

MECHANISMS OF FORMING THE INTELLECTUAL ABILITY OF PRE-SCHOOL STUDENTS THROUGH INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES

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In order to provide children with quality education in pre-school educational organizations, it is necessary to organize the educational process on the basis of innovative technologies. For this, it is necessary to harmonize all pedagogical technologies that serve to prepare the child for social life.

The quality of pre-school education guarantees the quality acquisition of knowledge by children at the next stages of education. For this, it is necessary to develop uniform requirements for raising the quality of preschool education to a new level. These requirements imply the creation of quality education and basic skills. Based on these requirements, education of children begins at the age of 3 and continues until the age of 7.

The principle of individualization of preschool education embodies a number of requirements. This is a unique natural process. Along with the development of the society, the activity of the individual is individualized to a greater extent and his position changes. If the country and society are developed, then each person will be valued separately and will have his place.

It is known that preschool education is aimed at comprehensive development of children. According to the requirements of the new era, preschool education is a social institution of a new form. Therefore, it should be convenient for children to participate and acquire certain knowledge and develop. The quality of pre-school education should be regularly analyzed from the point of view of the requirements of the time. In this process, basic knowledge and concepts are formed that have equal opportunities for all children.

Education, as a separate component of the structure of the global community, should take into account all the changes taking place in society, and change its structure and content of activity on this basis.

Today, the fact that education lags behind the pace of development of society, that the technologies used in the educational process do not fully meet modern requirements, is often recognized by the world community. Because education, as a socializer, should follow the changes in society and have an impact on its development. However, the relationship between the development of the society and the education system has a complex appearance and is distinguished by a high level of enthusiasm. Education does not accept the influence of all active and slow changes, but it has its influence on the events happening in society. From this point of view, changes in education are not only a result, but a condition for the future development of society.

It is known that today, when science and technology are developing at a rapid pace, the amount of scientific knowledge, understanding and imagination is increasing dramatically. This, on the one hand, ensures its differentiation due to the development of new fields and departments of science and technology, and on the other hand, creates the process of integration between sciences.

In such conditions, the demands for highly qualified pedagogues are increasing, who have the ability to educate a mature generation in the spirit of universal and national values that have been formed over the centuries, who have mastered the fundamentals of science,

pedagogy and psychology methods, who have a high level of professional training and modern pedagogical and It is necessary to train creative pedagogues with the skills and qualifications to apply information technologies in practice.

Currently, the wide application of pedagogical innovations in the educational process is a global trend of world development. Special attention is being paid to the systematic introduction of innovations in the field of education at the same time when the scope of pedagogical innovations is increasing and the modernization process is developing rapidly in the country. However, despite the fact that many pedagogical innovations are being created, the level of introducing pedagogical research on the application of new content, forms, methods and tools of teaching to educational processes cannot be considered sufficient.

In fact, in the introduction of the updated education system, every teacher should regularly study the innovations related to their subject and the education of the mature generation, and acquire the skills to apply them consistently in their work. is an important requirement of today. The experience of foreign countries was studied in connection with the activities aimed at the formation of the intellectual ability of the students, and a comparative analysis was made as follows. In Japan, a large part of the family budget is spent on ensuring that children receive a thorough education in kindergartens and universities. In the family, all conditions are created for the child to get a good education. During exams, children are freed from housework. Parents actively participate in all areas of school life, they are role models for their children in all areas. They study a lot to help their children study, they learn the school curriculum perfectly.

Mothers have a great role and responsibility in raising children. They consider themselves responsible to the family dynasty and the state for their children to grow up to be smart, wise, polite, fair and hardworking. In Japan, many methodical manuals and recommendations on family education are published, many pedagogical tips are given on radio and television. There are great opportunities for the child's independent and intellectual development during preschool education. In this process, it is important that the pedagogical activity is directed to support a specific child for his intellectual development. Directing pedagogical activity to a specific goal does not deny its existence, but expands its scope. Only concrete activity expressed in a specific result will bear fruit. Pedagogical activities of the educator should be in accordance with his goals, thoughts, and work style.

In the actions of educators, such cases are very rare. They are often combined with each other. The mutual harmony and interdependence of the factors that represent the reasons is the basis for the general slowness in the intellectual development of students of preschool educational organizations. Programs and pedagogical measures aimed at the intellectual development of children not only make the lessons interesting, but also make a special contribution to the intellectual development of children. For example, most boys initially have difficulties in writing letters and memorizing poems. At such times, they start to feel ashamed of their failures. As a result, they reluctantly participate in training. They don't even want to attend preschool.

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